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Potential of Cattle Dung Ash (CDA) against maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky, 1855 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) on stored maize (*Zea mays* L.)

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ABSTRACT

A study was conducted at the Laboratory of the Department of Agronomy, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe State, with the aim of determining the potentials of Cattle Dung Ash (CDA) against maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky, 1855) infestation on stored maize, and its ability to confer protection to maize grain while in storage. Three maize varieties (SAMMAZ 15, DMR and SAMMAZ 51) were sourced from the Gombe State Agricultural Development Programme (GSADP) station. Each of the stored maize varieties was treated with four levels (0g, 2g, 4g, 6g) of CDA, which was prepared by drying and burning until it became ash. They were each put in plastic containers covered with muslin and secured with rubber bands. The experiment was set up in the laboratory in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) under prevailing weather conditions, and replicated three times. Parameters that were determined from the experiment included adult *S. zeamais* mortality on stored maize treated with CDA, exit holes on *S. zeamais*-infested stored maize treated with CDA and weight loss on *S. zeamais*-infested stored maize treated with CDA. Results from the study showed that number of adult *S. zeamais* mortality showed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher mortalities, especially 4DAT and 6DAT compared with control treatment. However, number of adult *S. zeamais* mortality among maize varieties was not significant ($p > 0.05$). Interaction between treatment and variety was significant ($p \leq 0.05$) 4DAT. The study suggests that CDA possesses some insecticidal properties capable of protecting stored maize from infestation by *S. zeamais*.

Keywords: Cattle Dung Ash, stored maize, *Sitophilus zeamais*, Coleoptera

1. INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.), a key crop for millions of people across the globe (Akowuah *et al.*, 2018), belongs to the family Poaceae (Ogunsina *et al.*, 2011). It is highly cultivated around the world, especially Nigeria where it is used for multiple purposes (Akowuah *et al.*, 2018; Onuminya *et al.*, 2018; Olorunmota *et al.*, 2021). However, in spite of the importance of maize to consumers and industries, its cultivation and storage has been adversely affected by insect pests; thus reducing their nutritional, market and industrial values (Throne, 1994; Nukenine *et al.*, 2002; Demissie *et al.*, 2008). Mostly kept in stores postharvest, maize come under attack from a plethora of insect pests, especially *Sitophilus zeamais*, which is the most devastating storage pest of maize, causing serious management problem to farmers and storeowners alike (Adedire, 2001; Abulude *et al.*, 2007; Sagheer *et al.*, 2013).

In seeking for a solution to the menace of *S. zeamais* on stored maize, many workers have reported several measures, which can be employed in controlling the activities of these obnoxious insect pests (Goftishu and Belete, 2014; Khaliq *et al.*, 2015; Cosmas *et al.*, 2018).

These control measures present a significant shift from the use of chemical pesticides due to their negative impacts on human and animal health, the environment and non-target organisms (Ileke and Oni, 2011, Erenso, and Berhe, 2016; Buba and Muhammad, 2015). Other challenges of utilizing chemical pesticides for insect control include development of resistance in target insect pests (Suleiman, 2019); increased regulatory constraints and high cost of purchase (Oppert *et al.*, 2010). In the view of this, it has become necessary to seek for alternatives to chemical pesticides that are readily available, cheap, friendly to humans and non-target organisms, and not harmful to the environment (Buba *et al.*, 2023; Buba and Muhammad, 2025). Natural and plant products have been utilized by peasant farmers and traditional storeowners alike to control insect pests in some tropical countries (Erenso, and Berhe, 2016; Regmi *et al.*, 2020, Buba *et al.*, 2023). These naturally sourced pesticides have shown huge promise in controlling insect pests, especially in stored agricultural commodities (Buba *et al.* (2013; Sani and Suleiman, 2017; Kadi Kadi *et al.*, 2025). They act to protect stored products from insect pest infestation by repelling them, suppressing oviposition, suffocating them and causing mortality (Lawan *et al.*, 2016; Sani and Suleiman, 2017; Rosulu *et al.*, 2022).

One of the natural products being explored as an alternative to chemical pesticide for insect pest control is Cattle Dung Ash (CDA), which is obtained from cattle dung found all over the tropics, especially where animal husbandry is practiced (Patil *et al.*, 2023). Cattle Dung Ash possesses many qualities, which make it a good alternative to synthetic pesticides. One of these qualities include possessing insecto-repellant properties (Sharma and Singh, 2015; Ogban, 2020), due to its high silicon content, which is insecticidal (EPA, 1991, Silicon Dioxide and silica gel <https://archive.epa.gov/pesticide/registration>). In addition, it is also known to cause mortality in insect pests (Arya and Tiwari, 2013) by suppressing feeding abilities in insect pests, especially bruchids (Narayana *et al.*, 2019). It is in the light of the aforementioned that this research sets out to investigate the effect of CDA on *S. zeamais* on stored maize.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the laboratory of the Department of Agronomy, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University Kashere, Gombe State. Kashere lies between 9°46'N and

10°57'E in the tropical climate region with a mean annual rainfall of 943 mm mean annual temperature of 28 – 39 °C, mean humidity of 68% and on average.

2. 1. Sourcing of experimental materials

Maize weevil used for this study was obtained from infested maize grains sourced from the Gombe State Agricultural Development Programme (GSADP) station. Clean, whole and uninfested maize grains of three different varieties (SAMMAZ 15, DMR and SAMMAZ 51) used for the experiment were also purchased from GSADP.

2. 2. Collection and preparation of cattle dung ash

Cattle dung was collected at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University of Kashere. The cattle dung was sorted to remove solid contaminants and sundried. This was followed by crushing to smaller sizes and sun-drying and crushing into small particles and prepared as described by Suleiman and Haruna, (2020).

2. 3. Culture of *S. zeamais*

One kilogram of infested maize grains was put in three separate muslin-covered plastic containers. Each of the muslin was secured to the container with a rubber band to prevent escape of insects from the container, and allow for adequate aeration. These containers were allowed undisturbed for seven days for the trapped *S. zeamais* to mate, oviposit and emerge as adult culture (Buba *et al.*, 2023; Luz *et al.*, 2009; Pimentel *et al.*, 2009; Altemir *et al.*, 2011; Ruchuon & Waranyoo, 2022; Tarcísio *et al.*, 2022).

One hundred *S. zeamais* were picked from the prepared culture and introduced to uninfested maize grains weighing 1 kg placed in three containers. These were allowed to mate and oviposit until emergence of F₁ pristine adult *S. zeamais*. These were used for the experiments. Each maize variety, weighing 20g, was put in a plastic container. Three levels of CDA weighing 2g, 4g, and 6g were added to the containers and mixed thoroughly. A fourth plastic container without any CDA treatment (control) was also set up.

Twenty pristine adult *S. zeamais* were put in each plastic container, which was covered and secured with muslin cloth and rubber band respectively. Each of the treatments was replicated three times. The experiment was allowed to run for 8 days after treatment (DAT) with CDA.

2. 4. Data collection and parameters measured

2. 4. 1. Number of adult *S. zeamais* mortality on stored maize treated with CDA

The mortality of *S. zeamais* was inspected after every 2 days to remove, count and record dead adult *S. zeamais* for 8 days. Counted adult *S. zeamais* were discarded.

2. 4. 2. Exit holes on stored maize infested by *S. zeamais*

Number of exit holes on maize grains bored by *S. zeamais* were counted and recorded. This was done by randomly picking of 5 seeds of maize grains and counting. The mean exit hole numbers were calculated and recorded.

2. 4. 3. Weight loss of stored maize infested by *S. zeamais*

Both maize grains were sieved to remove the ash and any dust on the completion of eight days to determine maize grain weight loss. Grain weight losses were determined using the formula:

$$\text{Weight loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight} \times 100}{\text{Initial weight}}$$

2. 4. 4. Data analysis

Data were collected were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SAS Software Package and the mean difference was determined using Least Significance Difference (LSD) at 5% probability level.

3. RESULT

3. 1. Number of adult *S. zeamais* mortality on stored maize treated with CDA

Table 1 shows that at days four and six there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in Adults *S. zeamais* mortality when on SAMMAZ 15, DMR, and SAMMAZ 51. However, there was a highly significant ($p \leq 0.05$) at all CDA levels compared with control (0g) on days four and six. Interaction of variety CDA levels at 4DAT also showed a significantly high mortality of adult *S. zeamais* on stored maize.

Table 1. Number of adult *S. zeamais* mortality on stored maize grains when treated with CDA.

TREATMENTS	2DAT	4DAT	6DAT	8DAT
VARI ETIES				
SAMMAZ 15	1.583	3.833	7.750	3.666
DMR	1.500	4.083	8.666	3.000
SAMMAZ 51	1.500	5.166	7.833	2.916
LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANT (P≤0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS
L.S.D	1.2486	1.6209	2.1627	1.3052
CATTLE DUNG ASH				
0g	0.777	1.666	4.444	3.666
2g	1.666	4.666	9.889	2.777

4g	1.555	5.333	9.667	2.666
6g	2.111	5.777	8.333	3.666
LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANT (P≤0.05)	NS	**	**	NS
L.S.D	1.5927	2.0675	2.7586	1.6648
INTRACTION				
V X TRT	NS	*	NS	NS
DAT = Days After Treatment, LSD = Least Significant Difference, V = Variety, TRT = Treatment, NS = Not Significant				

3. 2. Number of exit holes on stored maize infested by *S. zeamais*

Table 2 Shows that there was no significant ($p>0.05$) difference on emergence holes on stored maize infested by *S. zeamais* when treated with CDA. The highest level of emergence holes was recorded at 2g on SAMMAZ 15 at day 2, followed by 0g on SAMMAZ 51 at day 6 and DMR at 0g, at day 4 and 8 respectively.

Table 2. Number of Exit Holes (E. H.) on stored maize grain treated with CDA.

TREATMENTS	2DAT	4DAT	6DAT	8DAT
VARIETY				
SAMMAZ 15	1.833	0.916	1.250	0.750
DMR	1.500	1.333	1.583	0.833
SAMMAZ 51	1.333	0.583	1.666	0.583
SIG (P≤0.05)	NS	*	NS	NS
L.S.D	0.8324	0.8149	1.2716	0.8664
CATTLE DUNG ASH				
0g	1.666	1.444	1.888	1.111
2g	1.888	1.111	1.555	0.444
4g	1.555	0.555	1.222	0.888
6g	1.111	0.666	1.333	0.444

LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANT (P≤0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS
L.S.D	1.0618	1.0394	1.6.219	1.1051
INTERACTION				
V X TRT	NS	NS	NS	NS
DAT = Days After Treatment, LSD = Least Significant Difference, V = Variety, TRT = Treatment, NS = Not Significant				

3. 3. Weight loss on stored maize due to infestation by adult *S. zeamais*

There was no significant ($p>0.05$) weight loss in all three varieties infested with *S. zeamais* in Table 3. However, weight loss between all CDA levels were significantly ($p\leq 0.05$) lower when compared with the control (0g) treatment.

Table 3. Weight loss on stored maize due to infestation by *S. zeamais*.

TREATMENTS	WEIGHT LOSS
VARIETY	
SAMMAZ 15	19.789
DMR	19.687
SAMMAZ 51	19.698
LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANT (P<0.05)	NS
L.S.D	0.2818
CATTLE DUNG ASH	
0g	18.985
2g	19.298
4g	19.589
6g	19.767
LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANT (P≤0.05)	*
L.S.D	0.3594

INTERACTION	
V X TRT	NS
LSD = Least Significant Difference, V = Variety, TRT = Treatment, NS = Not Significant	

4. DISCUSSION

The present study showed that CDA caused mortality of adult *S. zeamais* on stored maize. This is evident in the survival of adult *S. zeamais* on untreated stored maize grains (control treatment), unlike on CDA-treated stored maize grain where mortality were recorded. This is probably due to action of CDA antagonizing adult *S. zeamais* leading to mortality. This corresponds to the reports of Arya and Tiwari (2013) and Narayana *et al.* (2019) that CDA caused mortality on bruchids infesting maize by more than 90 per cent in 1 day. Additionally,

Suleiman and Haruna (2020) reported mortality of *S. zeamais* infesting stored maize grains when treated with various levels of CDA as against when untreated. Mortality of adult *S. zeamais* on CDA-treated maize was due to tiny particles of the treatment, which blocked insect spiracles hence interfering with respiration (Suleiman and Haruna, 2020). EPA (1991) further reported CDA containing high level of silicon making it highly insecticidal.

Maize damage evidenced by exit holes and weight loss shows no significant difference between all treatments except on day 8. This is probably due to the swift action and effectiveness of CDA, which acts immediately it is applied on stored maize. CDA is known to cause mortality on insect pests a day after application leaving no room for commodities to be damaged.

This is congruent with the finding of Narayana *et al.* (2019) that CDA caused about 93 per cent mortality in *Rhyzopertha dominica* in 24 hours. This again underscores the efficacy of CDA is conferring protection to stored maize against infestation by *S. zeamais*.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study showed the effectiveness of CDA against *S. zeamais* stored maize by causing mortality and suppressing damage and weight loss. In spite of variations in mortalities based on levels of the treatment, protection of the commodity from infestation was achieved. CDA is an effective natural control agent for controlling maize weevil *S. zeamais* on stored commodities, therefore its mechanism of action on insect pests should be further investigated to determine active ingredients it contains and the optimum level needed to confer the best protection from insect pests infestation.

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